

Reaction of Arylidencyanoacetamides with *p*-Tolyltetrachlorophosphorane

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Manuscript received 7 November 1979, revised 12 June 1980, accepted 7 August 1980

Arylidencyanoacetamides react with *p*-tolyltetrachlorophosphorane in refluxing carbon tetrachloride to give *N*-(arylidencyanoacetyl)-*p*-tolylphosphonimidic dichlorides. The structural assignments of the products were based on IR and chemical reactions.

In previous publications^{1,2}, we have described the reaction of arylidencyanoacetamides(I) with phosphorus pentachloride and phenyltetrachlorophosphorane. In this work, the reaction of compounds(I) with *p*-tolyltetrachlorophosphorane is investigated.

Thus, when compounds(I) were refluxed with *p*-tolyltetrachlorophosphorane(II) in carbon tetrachloride, until the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased (ca., 1.5 hr), they gave *N*-(arylidencyanoacetyl)-*p*-tolylphosphonimidic dichlorides(III).

The reaction of dichlorides(III) with aniline as well as with anhydrous formic acid yielded the corresponding dianilides(IV) and *N*-(arylidencyanoacetyl)-*p*-tolylphosphonamidic acid(V) respectively.

Ar, a = C₆H₅; b = *p*-CH₃OC₆H₄; c = *p*-ClC₆H₄; d = *m*-NO₂C₆H₄; e = *p*-NO₂C₆H₄; R = *p*-CH₃C₆H₄

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-5A unit as KBr pellets. *p*-Tolyldichlorophosphine³ and arylidencyanoacetamides⁴ were prepared according to known procedures.

N-(Arylidencyanoacetyl)-*p*-tolylphosphonimidic dichlorides(II):

General Procedure:

A suspension of 0.01 mole of arylidencyanoacetamides and 0.01 mole of *p*-tolyltetrachlorophosphorane in 50 ml carbon tetrachloride was refluxed until HCl evolution ceased, (ca., 1.5 hr), during which complete dissolution of the compounds

TABLE 1—*N*-(ARYLIDENCYANOACETYL)-*p*-TOLYLPHOSPHONIMIDIC DICHLORIDES(III) AND DIANILIDES(IV)

Compd.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	X	Formula	Analysis		I.R. ^a ν _{N=O}
						Calcd. %Cl	Found %Cl	
IIIa	H	80	71	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ OP	19.56	19.40	1294
b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	78	144	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ P	18.07	18.27	1286
c	<i>p</i> -Cl	85	142	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ N ₂ OP	26.79	26.54	1295
d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	76	165	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ P	17.40	17.21	1293
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	73	137	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ P	17.40	17.17	1300
						%N	%N	
IVa	H	92	195	C ₆ H ₅ NH	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₄ OP	11.76	11.69	1311
b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	86	184	C ₆ H ₅ NH	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ P	11.07	11.25	1305
c	<i>p</i> -Cl	88	200	C ₆ H ₅ NH	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OP	10.97	10.66	1312
d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	81	185	C ₆ H ₅ NH	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ P	13.44	13.21	1315
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	83	206	C ₆ H ₅ NH	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ P	13.44	13.23	1320

TABLE 2—N-(ARYLIDENECYANOACETYL)-*p*-TOLYLPHOSPHORAMIDIC ACIDS(V)

Compd.	R	Yield%	m.p.°C	Formula	Analysis		I.R. ⁴ ν _{P=O}
					Calcd. %N	Found %N	
Va	H	60	108	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₅ P	8.59	8.79	1247
b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	69	205	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅ P	7.86	7.66	1244
c	<i>p</i> -Cl	70	199	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₅ P	7.77	7.56	1250
d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	62	124	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅ P	11.32	11.44	1250
e	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	63	209	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅ P	11.32	11.57	1253

occurred. The solution was cooled to room temperature and the precipitate formed was collected and washed with carbon tetrachloride and crystallised from benzene or carbon tetrachloride. The prepared compounds are recorded in Table 1.

N-(Arylideneacyanoacetyl)-*p*-tolylphosphonimidic dianilides(IV) :

A solution of 4 mmol aniline in 10 ml benzene was gradually added at room temperature to a suspension of the dichlorides(III), 1 mmol in 30 ml benzene. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 hr and then refluxed for 2 hr. The solid was filtered, dried, washed well with water, dil. HCl, water and then crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (Table 1).

N-(Arylideneacyanoacetyl)-*p*-tolylphosphonamidic acids(V) :

A solution of 0.01 mole of the dichlorides(III) in dry benzene was treated with 0.02 mole of

anhydrous formic acid. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 hr and then refluxed for 2 hr. The precipitated solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

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